

Energy recovery and economic viability of animal-derived waste air gasification for syngas production

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Abstract. Animal-derived waste poses significant disposal and environmental challenges, yet its organic and mineral-rich composition offers opportunities for energy recovery through thermochemical valorization. Chicken bone waste (CBW), a byproduct of the poultry industry, was selected as a feedstock for conversion into energy. In this study, CBW was first processed via pyrolysis to produce a carbon-rich char, which was subsequently gasified with air at 700 °C in a lab-scale fixed-bed batch reactor to generate synthesis gas (syngas). The resulting syngas was rich in carbon monoxide (~43.5 % CO), carbon dioxide (~39.2 % CO₂), and moderate hydrogen fraction (~14.0% H₂). It exhibited a higher heating value (HHV) of approximately 25.87 MJ/kg, and the gasification achieved a cold-gas efficiency of ~54.6%, suggesting that over half of the feedstock's energy content was recovered in gaseous form. Based on these results, a conceptual pilot-scale system was analyzed, comprising a 100 kg/h gasifier and a 15.36 kW_e syngas turbine for power generation. Under the stated assumptions, the techno-economic analysis demonstrated economic viability for syngas utilization as an energy source, with net present value (NPV) ≈ 28554 € and internal rate of return (IRR) ≈ 15.3%. Sensitivity analyses were performed to capture the impact of technical and market variability. Increasing the syngas LHV (8.98–11.67 MJ/Nm³) enhanced NPV linearly. Improving electric turbine efficiency (30-40 %) produced the strongest effect, increasing NPV to ≈ 58700 € and IRR to ≈ 21 %, while reducing discounted payback period (DPP) to ≈ 6 years. Electricity price variation (0.09–0.15 €/kWh) identified a break-even tariff of ≈ 0.106 €/kWh, above which profitability rapidly improved. Overall, air gasification of CBW-derived biochar was shown to efficiently produce high-quality syngas for power generation. This waste-to-energy pathway is energy-efficient and economically viable, illustrating a practical approach to circular economic goals through the valorization of animal-derived waste.

Keywords: air gasification; animal-derived waste; biochar utilization; syngas production; techno-economic analysis; circular economy; waste-to-energy.

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Introduction

Animal-derived waste has increased considerably due to the rising demand for meat products, reaching up to 365 Mt in 2024 [1]. The largest consumption demand is for poultry meat, having an expected growth rate of 2.2 % each year and it is projected to reach 173 Mt by 2034 [1,2]. This growing demand for poultry meat generates large quantities of animal-derived waste, with chicken bone waste (CBW) posing a considerable environmental and logistical challenge. Conventional disposal methods, such as landfilling, are environmentally detrimental and economically costly. In

parallel, the global transition toward a low-carbon energy economy has intensified the demand for sustainable and renewable fuels.

Chicken bones are dense and highly mineralized, with a significant calcium–phosphate fraction that limits their direct combustion, which results in a high ash content and low energy yield [3]. Thermochemical processes such as pyrolysis and gasification enable the conversion of organic components into liquid or gaseous fuels, while simultaneously generating a mineral-rich char with potential applications such as fertilizer, adsorbent, catalysis support, and medical applications [4]. However, most research has focused on pyrolysis on meat-and-bone meal (MBM) and general poultry waste [5–7] rather than on air gasification of chicken bones [4,8].

Gasification of chicken bone waste

Gasification involves the partial oxidation of biomass at 350–1000 °C, producing synthesis gas (H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄) [9,10]. The yield and composition of the syngas are strongly influenced by operating temperature, choice of gasifying agent (air, O₂, steam, or CO₂), reactor configuration, and the presence of catalysts. Compared to pyrolysis, gasification generally enhances gaseous product generation and minimizes tar formation. Research on animal-derived wastes has mainly focused on meat-and-bone meal (MBM), pig bones, and poultry litter, while studies specifically addressing chicken bone waste remain scarce [4].

The literature on bone waste valorization demonstrates that processes like pyrolysis and calcination can recover valuable materials such as bone char, hydroxyapatite, calcium oxide, and phosphates [11]. These products have found applications as catalysts [12], adsorbents, and in agriculture as nutrient-rich fertilizers [4,13]. Unlike conventional biomass gasification projects that primarily generate revenue from energy alone, the gasification of chicken bone waste can create a dual-product revenue stream from both energy (syngas) and a high-value material (bone char) [11]. Previous literature reviews on animal-waste gasification identify meat-and-bone meal (MBM) as the most extensively studied feedstock [4]. For example, in MBM air gasification, increasing the temperature from 650 to 850 °C elevated hydrogen concentration from 5.5 to 7.3 vol % and carbon monoxide from 10 to 51.6 vol %, while carbon dioxide declined from 55 to 20.5 vol %. Under comparable conditions, steam gasification produced a greater hydrogen enhancement, rising from 42 to 52.2 vol %, alongside an increase in carbon monoxide from 10.2 to 26.8 vol % [4].

The present study aims to maximize the utilization of air gasification of animal bone biochar to produce syngas. This approach supports the global transition toward low-carbon and renewable energy systems, addressing the growing demand for sustainable gaseous fuels that can partially replace fossil-based energy sources. In this context, evaluating energy recovery efficiency and the economic feasibility of syngas utilization becomes essential [14]. Such assessments are typically carried out through techno-economic analysis, which integrates both the technological performance and the costs of the process to assess its scalability and competitiveness within the emerging green energy market [15]. The case study represents a pilot-scale conceptual example of the proposed waste-to-energy pathway. In industrial contexts, feedstock quantities are typically several orders of magnitude higher due to increased waste generation, resulting in a significantly greater potential for power generation.

Materials and Methods

Feedstock preparation and gasification

The feedstock used in this study was biochar derived from the pyrolysis of chicken bone waste (CBW). The raw CBW underwent a standard pretreatment protocol involving mechanical cleaning, drying, and grinding prior to pyrolysis. Residual meat, cartilage, and organic matter were manually removed, after which the cleaned bones were dried at 105 °C for 24 h in a laboratory oven (POL-EKO-APARATURA, Nitech) to eliminate moisture. The dried material was then ground to a uniform particle size. The resulting powder was subjected to slow pyrolysis at 700 °C, producing the CBW-derived biochar used as feedstock in the gasification experiments.

The gasification experiments were conducted in a batch tubular fixed-bed furnace (Nabertherm, model RO 60/750/13) [5,16] as depicted in Figure 1. The system is electrically heated and equipped with an internal ceramic tubular chamber, inside which a quartz reactor containing the feedstock was inserted.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the air gasification experimental setup. Source: Author's own contribution.

Each gasification run was conducted in batch mode using 3 g of biochar (C1) as feedstock. The sample was introduced into a preheated quartz reactor maintained at 700 °C. Prior to the introduction of the oxidizing agent, the reactor was thoroughly purged with nitrogen (N₂) to eliminate residual oxygen and prevent premature oxidation of the biochar. Once the target temperature was stabilized, compressed air was introduced at an equivalence ratio (E.R.) of 0.3 as the gasifying medium, delivered through a mass-flow-controlled system to ensure precise regulation of the oxidant flow rate. The total gasification duration was 10 minutes, during which syngas samples were collected at one-minute intervals for compositional analysis. To enhance gas–solid interactions, a high-temperature-resistant quartz-fiber permeable mesh was positioned within the reactor. This configuration reduced the superficial gas velocity, thereby increasing the residence time of the evolving gases within the reaction zone and promoting more effective gas–solid contact and conversion.

Syngas analysis

The syngas composition was determined using INFICON MicroGC Fusion. To isolate the process syngas, the contribution of N₂ introduced during the purging stage was excluded, and the remaining species were re-normalized to 100%. The syngas energy content was evaluated from its heating value, using normalized volume fractions and literature calorific constants for each combustible species [17,18].

Techno-economic evaluation and sensitivity analysis

The techno-economic assessment was carried out under the following assumptions. The project lifetime was set at 10 years with a discount rate of 7.5%. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) was fixed and considered as the initial investment, entirely self-financed (without credit or interest charges) and commissioned in the first year. The operating and maintenance (OPEX) costs were assumed constant at 3 % of CAPEX for each year of the project's lifespan. Moreover, the total electric annual energy output and the electricity price (p_e) were assumed to be constant each year, and therefore the revenue generated as well.

The gasification unit operates 8000 h/year at full capacity, achieving a cold-gas efficiency of 54.6% and a turbine electrical efficiency of 30%. All generated electricity is sold to the grid at a constant tariff of 0.14 €/kWh [19]. The specific investment costs were 1000 €/kW_t for the gasifier and 1500 €/kW_e for the syngas turbine. The feedstock, derived from chicken-bone waste, was considered a zero-cost material, and no subsidies, taxes, or inflation effects were included. Residual value, carbon credits, and externalities were excluded for simplicity.

To evaluate economic performance, a sensitivity analysis was performed by varying key parameters within realistic operational ranges. The syngas lower heating value (LHV) was varied by ±30% around the experimental value (8.98 MJ/Nm³), simulating process optimization through higher temperature, improved catalyst activity, or adjusted equivalent ratio. The turbine efficiency was increased from 30% to 40% to reflect potential design improvements or waste-heat recovery integration. Finally, the electricity selling price was varied between 0.09 and 0.15 €/kWh to capture market and policy fluctuations. For each case, the model recalculated system power output, CAPEX, OPEX, revenues, and financial indicators, including net present value (NPV, €), internal rate of return (IRR, %) and discounted payback period (DPP, years).

Results and Discussion

Syngas composition

Table 1 shows the average syngas composition obtained from six replicate runs. The gas mixture is predominantly composed of CO (~43.5 vol %), CO₂ (~39.2 vol %) and H₂ (~14 vol %). Light hydrocarbons represent only a minor fraction (~2.9 vol %), while CH₄ is nearly negligible (0.32 vol %). This distribution is expected since the feedstock consisted of biochar derived from the pyrolysis of CBW. During pyrolysis, most volatile compounds and condensable hydrocarbons are removed, resulting in a carbon-rich biochar, which after gasification primarily yields CO, CO₂, and H₂. Therefore, the gas composition reflects the gasification reactions of the char matrix, rather than a combined pyrolysis–gasification process. The high yield of CO₂ may indicate a slightly over-oxidizing process. Overall, the obtained gas species distribution is consistent with values typically reported for air gasification of biomass-derived chars in the literature [20,21].

Table 1: Syngas composition of the air gasification of CBW char. Source: Authors' own research.

Gas species	Vol %
H ₂	14.01
CO	43.53
CH ₄	0.32
CO ₂	39.20
Hydrocarbons	2.93

Syngas heating value

Figure 2 shows the calculated heating values of the syngas (HHV = 25.87 MJ/kg, LHV = 24.14 MJ/kg; HHV = 9.51 MJ/Nm³, LHV = 8.98 MJ/Nm³) indicate a medium-calorific gas, consistent with typical air-gasified biomass syngas. The relatively low difference between HHV and LHV (~1.7 MJ/kg and ~0.53 MJ/Nm³ respectively) suggests that losses due to the latent heat of water vaporization are limited. This behavior is characteristic of syngas mixtures dominated by CO and H₂, in which hydrogen oxidation contributes with less condensable water compared to hydrocarbon-rich gases. The low hydrocarbon fraction observed in the present study (CH₄ ≈ 0.3 vol %, C₂⁺ ≈ 2.9 vol %) further supports this conclusion. In comparison with literature, the present syngas heating values align with those reported for biochar gasification systems operating at 700–900 °C, where the LHV typically lies between 8 and 10 MJ/Nm³ [22,23].

Figure 2: Comparison between higher (HHV) and lower (LHV) heating values of the syngas on a mass basis (MJ/kg) and volumetric basis (MJ Nm⁻³). Source: Author's own contribution (OriginPro[®] Software).

Energy and Mass Flow Balances

During gasification, 3 g of biochar produced 2.36 g of ash, indicating a mass loss of 0.64 g. Assuming this lost mass corresponds to carbon gasified into CO, CO₂ and minor hydrocarbons, the experiment generated roughly 0.00113 m³ of syngas. Scaling up to specific volume, this equates to approximately 0.38 Nm³ of syngas per kilogram of CBW biochar. The overall cold gas efficiency (CGE), defined as the fraction of feedstock energy recovered in the syngas, can be calculated using eq. (2).

$$CGE = \frac{LHV_{\text{syngas}} \left(\frac{MJ}{m^3} \right) \times V_{\text{syngas}} (m^3)}{LHV_{\text{biochar}} \left(\frac{MJ}{kg} \right) \times m_{\text{biochar}} (kg)} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Knowing that the LHV of the biochar is 6.18 MJ/kg [7]. Therefore, the CGE of the gasification installation is 54.6 %.

Techno-economic evaluation

The techno-economic evaluation of a small-scale gasification system was conducted using a continuous biochar feed rate of 100 kg/h, resulting in a syngas production capacity of 902 Nm³/day. Based on the experimentally determined lower heating value (LHV = 8.98 MJ/Nm³), the total chemical energy available in the generated syngas corresponds to a thermal input of 93.7 kW_t. Considering the measured gasification installation efficiency of 54.6 %, the effective thermal energy output is approximately 51.2 kW_t, confirming that more than half of the feedstock's energy content is successfully converted into usable gas-phase energy carriers. The system assumed a continuous 24-hour operation, corresponding to an annual utilization time of 8000 h/year. Under these conditions, the total thermic annual energy output is estimated at 409.6 MWh_t/year, which provides the basis for downstream energy recovery via electrical conversion in a syngas turbine.

From an economic perspective, the specific investment cost for the gasification installation was assumed to be 1000 €/kW_t, yielding a gasifier CAPEX of 51194 € for the 51.2 kW_t thermal system. Fixed operating costs for maintenance, services, and management were assumed to be 3% of CAPEX, corresponding to 1535.8 €/year for the gasifier. The syngas turbine delivering 15.36 kW_e and an electric annual energy output of 122867 kWh_e/year (based on a 30 % electrical efficiency) was evaluated separately at a specific cost of 1500 €/kW_e, giving a turbine CAPEX of 23037 € and a fixed OPEX of 691.1 €/year. The total investment and operational costs (CAPEX and OPEX) of the system were determined as the sum of the thermal and electrical subsystems. These aggregated values were then used to estimate the project's economic indicators. Table 2 summarizes the economic indicators resulting from the economic evaluation.

Table 2: Economic parameters and indicators resulted in the techno-economic evaluation. Source: Authors' own research.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Total capital expenditure (CAPEX)	74231	€
Total operational costs (OPEX)	2227	€/year
Yearly revenue	14975	€/year
Net present value (NPV)	28554	€
Internal rate of return (IRR)	15.32	%
Gross payback period (GPP)	5.96	years
Discounted payback period (DPP)	7.44	years

At an assumed electricity tariff of 0.14 €/kWh, the annual electricity production (122880 kWh/year) yields revenues of 17203 €/year; after OPEX (2226.9 €/year), the net annual cash flow is 14976 €/year, corresponding to a payback period of ~7.4 years. For a 7.5 % discount rate and 10-year project life, the NPV ≈ 28554 €, IRR ≈ 15.3 %, indicating profitability under these assumptions.

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis examined how variations in syngas quality, turbine efficiency, and electricity selling price influence the economic viability of the proposed small-scale air gasification system. The baseline case (LHV = 8.98 MJ/Nm³; $\eta_e = 30\%$; $p_e = 0.14$ €/kWh) demonstrates an economic basis for waste-to-energy conversion.

Figure 3: Sensitivity analysis of the variation of LHV (a), syngas turbine efficiency (b), and electricity price (c). Source: Author's own contribution (OriginPro® Software).

Increasing the syngas LHV from 8.98 to 11.67 MJ/Nm³ (+30%) directly improved the energy output and associated revenues. Electrical production increased from 122.9 MWh/year to 159.7 MWh/year, while annual revenues increased from 17201 €/year to 22362 €/year. The resulting NPV increased linearly from 28555 € to 37120 €, whereas the IRR (15.3%) and payback time (~6 years) remained constant due to proportional increases in investment and income. This confirms that improvements in gas composition can translate directly into higher profitability without increasing financial risk.

The turbine efficiency showed the strongest influence on profitability. As η_e increased from 30% to 40%, the annual electricity generation rose from 122.9 MWh/year to 163.823 MWh/year, resulting in revenue growth from 17201 €/year to ~22,935 €/year. Although the total CAPEX increased by approximately 10%, the additional income offset this cost increase, raising NPV from 28555 € to 58651 € and IRR from 15.3% to 21.41%. The payback period decreased from 7.44 to 5.93 years. These results demonstrate that improvements in turbine performance (2–10%) can substantially enhance project profitability, making the conversion efficiency a critical design parameter.

Electricity price sensitivity revealed the expected linear correlation between tariff level and profitability. At the lowest tested tariff (0.09 €/kWh), the project becomes unprofitable (NPV = -13615 €; IRR = 3.3%; payback time over the 10-year lifespan). Profitability turns positive near the 0.11 €/kWh threshold (NPV = 3335 €; IRR = 8.5%, payback time = 10.41 years) and improves steadily at higher prices. At 0.13–0.15 €/kWh, the project achieves NPV = 20000–37000 € and IRR = 13–17.5%, with payback times reduced to 8.12–6.83 years. Thus, maintaining a sale or offset price of ≥ 0.13 €/kWh ensures economic returns under current Romanian market conditions.

Conclusion

The experimental results confirm that chicken bone waste-derived char is a viable gasification feedstock for syngas production. Efficient energy recovery was achieved, with over 50% of the char's energy content was captured in the syngas (cold-gas efficiency >50%). The product gas was of good quality, containing a high proportion of CO (~43%) and a moderate H₂ fraction (~14%), which contributed to a heating value of ~25.9 MJ/kg. This syngas composition and energy content demonstrates its suitability for combustion-based power generation. Scaling up the process to a 100 kg/h gasifier coupled with a 15.36 kW_e syngas turbine is projected to maintain a high overall energy recovery (exceeding 50% of feedstock energy as useful syngas and electricity).

The techno-economic analysis confirmed that the air gasification of chicken-bone-derived biochar represents a technically feasible and economically viable option for energy production. Under baseline conditions (LHV = 8.98 MJ/Nm³; $\eta_e = 30\%$; $p_e = 0.14$ €/kWh), the system achieved an NPV of 28554 €, an IRR of 15.3%, and

a discounted payback period of 7.4 years, demonstrating a positive investment profile even without external incentives. Sensitivity analyses revealed that profitability is most strongly influenced by turbine efficiency and electricity price, while syngas quality (LHV) has a secondary but proportional effect. Improvements of 2–10 % in turbine efficiency or electricity tariff can increase NPV up to 58651 € and shorten the payback period to 5.9 years.

Future work should focus on process integration, such as combining the pyrolysis and gasification stages, which could be explored to improve overall efficiency and simplify operations. In addition, gas cleaning measures will be needed to ensure the syngas meets quality requirements for stable turbine operation and to minimize emissions. The residual mineral ash could also be explored for potential applications in agriculture or industry, further enhancing the circular economic benefits. Although this case study represents a conceptual example, in real industrial contexts the available feedstock quantities are significantly higher, offering much greater potential for power generation and environmental impact reduction.

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